

Research article

Another contribution to the hypothesis for Austronesian toponyms in Vietnam

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Abstract: This paper employs historical phonological evidence and geographical linguistic maps to examine specific toponyms in Vietnam, including Phú Gia, Bà Đanh, Sầu - Giá, and Hà Lầm, Hà Lam, Kha Lâm, Khả Lâm, in order to further investigate the contact between Vietnamese and Austronesian speakers. Two main hypotheses have been posited regarding the origins of Austronesian toponyms, particularly those found in Northern Vietnam. The first suggests that the toponyms resulted from early contact during Austronesian migrations to Southeast Asia. The second posits that contact occurred later, possibly after the 10th century during Đại Việt's conquests of the Champa region, leading to the migration of Cham prisoners into the Northern Delta. Drawing on cultural and historical knowledge, this paper suggests Phú Gia, Bà Đanh, and Sầu - Giá likely emerged from language contact post-10th century. However, further study is needed for toponyms with Lâm/Lam/Lầm/Lãm. The findings also suggest that the presence of Austronesian-speaking residents in Northern Vietnam in antiquity is evident, though their migration timelines and directions remain debated.

Keywords: Austronesian; toponym; linguistic map; migration

1. Introduction

According to archaeological research results, the northern region of Vietnam has been inhabited by humans for a long time. There is substantial consensus among scholars such as Gourou (1936), C.Cœdès (1938) (See Nguyễn Văn Huyền 1944), K.Taylor (1983), Hà Văn Tấn (1997), M.Alves (2021) regarding the view that early Vietnamese residents in the Northern Delta region were not a homogeneous community, but had interactions with diverse communities speaking different languages.

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In his book *Les Paysans du delta Tonkinois* (*The Farmers of the Tonkinese Delta: A Study of Human Geography*), P. Gourou (1936) remarked that "researching and investigating toponyms seems to often lead to disappointment; unlike Europe, where toponyms are often ancient and offer valuable insights into successive waves of immigration that have shaped a country, in Tonkin as well as in China, toponyms frequently change and are often arbitrary and artificial creations. (...) Many villages also possess customary names alongside official ones. (...) Some of these customary names bear little resemblance to the official names, whether they are vestiges of ancient toponyms or manifestations of an ancient language—because some of these customary names sometimes assume peculiar forms. Addressing these inquiries necessitates a deep understanding of Vietnamese, Tày, and Chinese languages" (See Gourou 2017, pp. 137-138). This observation by Gourou appears to recognize that the Vietnamese language has been influenced by neighboring languages, particularly Chinese (Sino-Tibetan family) and Tày (Tai-Kadai language family), and that ancient toponyms may serve as evidence of linguistic interactions in antiquity.

In a study of the Phùng Nguyên culture (starting around 2000 BCE), based on the characteristics of stone tools, Hà Văn Tấn (1997) hypothesized "the Phùng Nguyên tribes, the core to form the Vietnamese ethnic community... spoke a dialect of the pro-Austroasiatic language family but were greatly influenced by the two Proto-Tai and Proto-Malayo-Polynesian language families" (Hà Văn Tấn 1997, p.370). But it should be noted that the author is also very cautious when making the above statement because, according to him, "finding the languages of ancient tribes is always difficult" and "documents about Phùng Nguyên culture are still very limited. Many reconstructions are, rather, just hypotheses" (Hà Văn Tấn 1997, p.379).

It can be said that Northern Vietnam is currently a concentrated residence of mainly Austroasiatic speakers, but in fact that is an Austroasiatic community which have undergone a most extraordinary developmental process and contact with other languages, specifically Tai-Kadai, Austronesian (Malayo-Polynesian), Sino-Tibetan and later European languages. Researching language contact in Vietnam in particular, in Southeast Asia in general with a diachronic approach has never been a simple task and the results and achievements have never satisfied scholars. Thus, studying toponyms can help to shed light on the issues of historical linguistics as well as hypotheses about the population migration in prehistoric and early historical periods. This paper delves into some toponyms in Vietnam to determine the origin of these toponyms and interpret the distributions of those toponyms on maps. The findings may help to enhance our understanding of the language contact between Vietnamese and Austronesian speakers and migration of Austronesian speakers to Northern Vietnam.

2. Data analysis

So far, there have been several published studies discussing the Austronesian toponyms in Vietnam, aiming at not only etymological issues but also the language as well as culture contact. Trần Trí Dõi is one of the authors who pays a lot of attention to this topic. In his studies, (2001a, 2001b, 2005, 2007) (See Trần Trí Dõi 2022) he indicated that toponyms with Cán/Càn/Cờn/Gàn and toponyms Cỗ Loa, Cà Lò, Cửa Lò all originated from Austronesian languages. He also argued that the groups of Cỗ Loa, Cà Lò, Cửa Lò related to the form “kolo/klo” which means “river mouth, estuary” in Austronesian languages and Cán/Càn/Cờn/Gàn might derive from “ikan” which means “fish” in Austronesian languages. These toponyms, especially river names and estuary names, might have appeared very early and be “the most durable and oldest names compared to other toponyms such as mountain names, names of resident or settlement places, etc.... only where there is water can people live” (Hoàng Thị Châu 2004, p.5).

Trần Thị Hồng Hạnh (2019) studied the Nôm toponyms Sinh of the Lại Ân village (Thừa Thiên Huế) which is now used to name the waterfront, local market as well the folk woodcut painting produced here. In this study, this toponym was identified to derive from *ching*. In Cham language, *ching* means “to cut, to carve, to engrave”. The phonetic form [cip] corresponds to the phonetic form [ɕip²] of Sinh, which allows to hypothesize that this village toponym might have originated from a Cham word which refers to the village’s famous craft-making wood carving pictures.

In an investigation into the toponym Phú Gia, Trương Nhật Vinh (2020) showed that cultural, geographical information and especially historical linguistics helped to demonstrate that Phú Gia might be a name of Cham origin. Phú Gia 富家 is an ancient village located northwest of West Lake, along the Red River, which is now the area of Phú Gia Ward and Phú Thượng Ward, Tây Hồ district, Hanoi. The village also has a folk name of Kê Gạ. Researching historical records and documents, he discovered that the village had three names: Phú Gia, Đa Gia Li and Bà Già. The name Phú Gia appeared as early as the 18th century. Meanwhile, names Đa Gia Li and Bà Già might be used as early as the late 11th century and continued to be used until around the mid-17th century. The reconstructed form of Đa Gia Li might be /*dua ia lich/ or /dua ia ling/, which in Cham language means “a village located between two floodwaters/two rivers that cause damage floods” (and the two rivers that might be referred to the Red River and Thiên Phù River).

Using the same method from an interdisciplinary approach with a focus on historical linguistics, Trương Nhật Vinh (2023) explained the origins and meaning of another toponym Bà Đanh, the name of a famous pagoda in Northern Vietnam. He indicated

that Bà Đanh was the result of the Vietnamization process of the Cham goddess named Po Yang Dari.

Map 1. The distribution of Bà Đanh toponyms in Northern Vietnam (Trương Nhật Vinh 2023)

In another recent study, Trương Nhật Vinh offered an explanation for the toponyms Sầu-Giá, two clusters of villages located adjacent to each other in Hoài Đức district, Hanoi today (Trương Nhật Vinh 2024). The Sino-Vietnamese names of the villages and communes in the Sầu-Giá region include Yên Sở, Đắc Sở, Dương Liễu, Mậu Hòa, and Quế Dương. These toponyms were documented quite early compared to other Sino-Vietnamese toponyms of villages and communes in the Red River Delta. According to him, the name Giá might be a Vietnamese adaptation of the form *ia/êa, which means "water" in Cham language, indicating a village located near a water source. The geographical location of Yên Sở village along the banks of the Đáy River and the presence of Cỗ Sở/Yên Sở wharf today (close to Quán Giá) further support his hypothesis. Additionally, he posited that the toponym Giá, as a Vietnamized name, implies that Giá village was situated in a low-lying area.

In contrast, Vinh suggested that the toponym Sầu village originated from the Vietnamization of the Cham word "chaur", meaning "high pile/dunes of soil". His fieldwork revealed that Sầu village is a large settlement, encompassing both inside and outside the dike. The inner part of the dike features a system of markets, communal houses, pagodas, while the outer part is known as the "new village". The village's terrain is higher compared to surrounding areas. Moreover, the prevalence of water wells built using Cham techniques and the abundance of coconut trees in the village support the notion that Sầu derives from Cham language, reflecting the topographical characteristics of the village situated on higher ground.

In his studies, Trương Nhật Vinh asserted that the commonality among these toponyms - *Phú Gia*, *Bà Đanh*, and *Sấu-Giá* - is that they all resulted from language contact between Vietnamese and Austronesian languages (specifically Cham) after the 10th century. There is a consensus among scientists that contact between speakers of Austroasiatic languages (specifically Vietnamese) and Austronesian languages could have occurred in two possible ways. The first possibility is early contact before Vietnamese separated into an independent language. At this stage, contact likely occurred during the migration of Austronesian-speaking populations.

Currently, there are differing opinions about the homeland of Austronesian languages. Some authors argue their origin is in mainland Asia (Kern 1889), specifically Southeastern China (Haudricourt 1954, Bellwood 1984-1985, Blust 1984-1985) (See Hà Văn Tấn 1997). Others suggest their homeland might be the islands of Southeast Asia (Solheim 1984-1985; Meacham 1984-1985). Meanwhile, according to Hà Văn Tấn (1997), their homeland might be in Southeastern China and the coastal areas of Southeast Asia (including Vietnam). He even suggests that "the creators of the Bàu Tró culture may have spoken an Austronesian language" (Hà Văn Tấn 1997, p. 584). The Bàu Tró culture is a late Neolithic culture (3000-2500 BCE) found along the coast from Nghệ An to Thừa Thiên Huế today.

Map 2. The distribution of Sấu – Giá and Phú Gia toponyms

The second possibility is contact after Vietnamese had essentially become an independent language. This occurred during Đại Việt's feudal state military campaigns into the Champa region. As a result of these conflicts, a large number of Cham prisoners of war migrated northward, settled, and assimilated with Vietnamese residents in the Red River Delta. This contact is recorded in Vietnamese history, notably in the 11th century when King Lý Thánh Tông resettled prisoners "from Vĩnh Khang prefecture to Đăng Châu, establishing villages with names reminiscent of ancient Chiêm Thành"

(Ngô Sĩ Liên 2010, p. 165). In our latest studies, we focused on four administrative toponyms: *Hà Lãm* (Quảng Ninh province), *Kha Lãm* (Hải Phòng city), *Khả Lãm* (Nghệ An province) and *Hà Lam* (Quảng Nam province). (Trần Thị Hồng Hạnh & Trương Nhật Vinh 2024). Firstly, in terms of geographical location, there is a coincidence as they are all situated near water sources. *Hà Lãm* is located near Cửa Lục Bay, a small bay within the Hạ Long Bay system. Four small rivers – Diễn Vọng River, Vũ Oai River, Man River, and Trới River – flow into Cửa Lục Bay and then into Hạ Long Bay. *Kha Lãm* is situated along the banks of Lạch Tray River. *Khả Lãm* (or Hương Lãm) is located along the banks of Cả River. *Hà Lam* is positioned between Trường Giang River and Rù Rì River (also known as Ly Ly River). Therefore, whether they are located in coastal areas (*Hà Lãm*), plains (*Kha Lãm*, *Hà Lam*), or foothills (*Khả Lãm* / *Hương Lãm*), these place names are all near rivers. This characteristic is crucial for us to further investigate the linguistic features (phonetic forms and meanings) of these place names. Secondly, these toponyms all consist of two syllables. The second syllables "Lam", "Lãm", "Lãm" are quite similar. There is a slight difference in the first syllable between "Hà" and "Kha/Khả". Trần Trí Dõi (2007) proposed that the second syllable in Sino-Vietnamese toponyms often reflects the phonetic form of the whole proto-Vietic syllable but the first syllable in Sino-Vietnamese toponyms often relates to the initial in proto-Vietic syllable. In our survey of several Austronesian languages, we found that the phonetic forms "hule/halau/halow/hlao" all have meanings related to water or water sources.

Table 1 Forms related to water or water sources in some Austronesian languages

Language	Word	Meaning
Indonesian	hule/hulu	river source
Raglai	halau	source
Cham	halau/halow	source
Jrai	hlào	source
Ede	hnoh	stream, source

The phonetic similarities between "hule/halau/halow/hlao" and the toponyms *Hà Lãm*, *Hà Lam*, *Kha Lãm*, and *Khả Lãm*/*Hương Lãm* suggest a hypothesis that the first syllable in these toponyms may preserve remnants of the initial part, while the second syllable retains remnants of the latter part of the phonetic forms in Austronesian languages. There is a correspondence in the initial and medial consonant sounds of these phonetic forms. Regarding *Kha Lãm* and *Khả Lãm*/*Hương Lãm*, further discussion is needed to explore the possibility of correspondence between the initial consonant in the first syllable and the initial consonant in the phonetic forms from Austronesian languages. This discussion involves the comparison between /χ/ and /h/. In current Vietnamese phonetics, /χ/ is described as a velar fricative, while /h/ is a

glottal fricative. However, in a historical linguistic study, Nguyễn Tài Cẩn (1995) noted that /h/ in Sino-Vietnamese words originates from two velar fricatives in Chinese, specifically /ɣ/ and /χ/. Nguyễn Tài Cẩn also observed, "In An Nam dịch ngữ, out of 22 cases with initial /h/, it was translated through /χ/ up to 20 times" (Nguyễn Tài Cẩn 1995, p. 100). Therefore, tentative acceptance of the correspondence in the initial consonant can be considered here. The differences in final consonants and tones are understandable and common in the process of Sino-Vietnamese adaptation of toponyms in Vietnam. Furthermore, the meanings of these words in Austronesian languages and the actual geographical locations of these places strongly support our hypothesis. Consequently, it is hypothesized that the toponyms Hà Lâm (Quảng Ninh), Kha Lâm (Hải Phòng), Khả Lãm/Hương Lãm (Nghệ An), and Hà Lam (Quảng Nam) might have originated from Austronesian languages.

Map 3. Distribution of toponyms Hà Lâm, Kha Lâm, Khả Lãm, Hà Lam

Based on the research results mentioned above, the distribution of toponyms hypothesized to have Austronesian origins is represented in maps 3a and 3b below.

Map 3a. Distribution of Austronesian toponyms Map 3b. Distribution of Austronesian toponyms

3. Discussions and suggestions

The distribution shown on map 4a supports Truong Nhat Vinh's claim regarding the origins of the toponyms *Sầu-Giá*, *Phủ Gia*, and *Bà Đanh*. These place names likely originated from interactions between Austronesian and Vietnamese communities in Northern Vietnam after the 10th century. In essence, these toponyms can be viewed as manifestations of Austronesian migration from Central Vietnam to the North. However, it is important to note that not all cases necessarily follow to this diffusion pattern. We aim to delve further into the cases of *Kha Lâm* and *Hà Lâm*. In the case of these two toponyms, the distribution depicted in map 3b suggests that they may have originated from a different historical diffusion process. This assumption is supported by additional archaeological evidence.

Map 4. Distribution of toponyms Kha Lâm, Hà Lâm

The ancient village of *Kha Lâm* is located in Nam Sơn ward, Kiến An district, Hải Phòng city. Situated at the base of Đầu Sơn mountain, which is now part of the expansive Thiên Văn mountain and forest complex, the village is notable for its cultural significance. Within Kha Lâm, a variety of architectural structures including communal houses, temples, and pagodas showcase sophisticated designs. These sites commemorate prominent historical figures who have made significant contributions to the nation, and many of them have been designated as heritage sites. One such example is the Kha Lâm temple dedicated to Princess Chiêu Chinh of the Trần dynasty. *Hà Lâm* is a ward in Hạ Long city, Quảng Ninh province, Vietnam. As mentioned above, *Hà Lâm* area specifically lies on the eastern side of Cửa Lục Bay, a small bay within the Hạ Long Bay system. Both of these toponyms are located within the cultural space of Hạ Long – Hải Phòng, where archaeologists have established that this area is not only a natural wonder but also a cradle of prehistoric civilization. Numerous archaeological research has revealed that stone tools, ceramic containers, stone jewelry, and bones found and collected in Hạ Long all date back to the late Neolithic period. Among them, an important study by Heine Geldern from the early 20th century can be mentioned.

Heine Geldern synthesized all contemporary knowledge about surveying archeology, ethnology, and linguistics to build a panorama of Southeast Asia. He placed particular emphasis on the study of cultures and populations, developing a model grounded in diffusionism. Heine Geldern focused on elucidating two pivotal stages in the cultural evolution of Southeast Asia: the Neolithic and Metal Ages. According to his research, the late Neolithic period in Southeast Asia witnessed the emergence of three successive cultural phases among distinct ethnic groups: the cylindrical axe culture (Walzenbeilkultur) among Papuan-speaking populations, the shoulder axe culture (Schulterbeilkultur) among Austronesian-speaking groups, and the quadrilateral axe culture (Vierkantbeilkultur) also among Austronesian speakers. Geldern's scholarly attention was particularly drawn to the migratory patterns of Austronesian peoples originating from China, dispersing across Indochina, Malaysia, and into the maritime regions of Southeast Asia and Oceania. He argued that each of these cultural groups exhibited distinct material and spiritual elements, thereby suggesting that cultural transformations in this region occurred primarily through diffusion and replacement processes (See Phạm Đình Mạnh 2007). While his opinions exerted a profound and enduring influence on contemporary prehistorians and successive generations of his students, they are now considered untenable. However, our special attention is given to his views because they include mention of shoulder axe culture (Schulterbeilkultur) and the quadrilateral axe culture (Vierkantbeilkultur) among the Austronesian speakers. Heine Geldern believed that the owner of the quadrangular ax culture in Southern China was of Austronesian origin. From here they migrated down the Southeast Asian

continent to the Malay peninsula, through Sumatra to Java, to the eastern islands of Indonesia, and then to the Indo-Pacific region.

In Vietnam, these two types of axes, shoulder axe culture (*Schulterbeilkultur*) and the quadrilateral ax culture (*Vierkantbeilkultur*), have been discovered in many archaeological sites across the country, including in Hạ Long. At Hạ Long site, archaeologists also found stone axes with shoulders with small shapes and sizes resembling those found in Guangdong, Fujian and Hong Kong. According to Trình Năng Chung (2008), the late Neolithic period in the coastal region of Southeast China is characterized by distinctive cultural artifacts such as printed ceramics, axes, shouldered stone axes, and stepped stone axes. Scholars have identified a close association between this region and the Hạ Long culture, which is found in the coastal plains and islands of Bái Tử Long and Hạ Long bays. In Guangxi province, the late Neolithic period is marked by the prevalence of the large stone shovel culture, primarily in the Guinan region. Trình Năng Chung suggested multiple instances of interaction between the Neolithic communities of Guinan and the Hạ Long culture inhabitants. He proposes that these interactions occurred via maritime routes, while with residents of Mai Pha crossing the Kỳ Cùng River and those from Hà Giang using the Bằng River and Gâm River passages (Trình Năng Chung 2008, p. 65). Trình Năng Chung (2008) stated that the stone shovel relics discovered in southern China date back mainly to the late Neolithic period, spanning from approximately 5,000 years ago to the Western Han period (2nd century AD). Vietnamese archaeological records document 37 instances of stone shovel relics across seven northern mountainous provinces and the northeastern coastal region of Vietnam. In the Hạ Long cultural area, the stone shovel are considered products of interaction and exchange. Due to its natural geographical location, this region facilitated extensive multi-directional contacts between the creators of the large stone shovel culture in southern China and the inhabitants of the Hạ Long culture. These interactions primarily occurred via maritime routes and secondarily through overland routes originating from the Lang Son area.

Luong Ninh (2010) asserted that archaeologists generally place the origins of the Austronesian people in a period dating back to 8,000-6,000 years BCE, with some proposing even earlier dates, while the closest evidence suggests a timeframe around 5,000-4,000 years BCE. However, archaeological findings in Vietnam indicate developments dating from approximately 3,000 years BCE, with peak concentrations around 500 years BCE. A. Reid has noted the involvement of the Chamic people in these migrations, but regardless of their origins, whether from the coast of Vietnam or elsewhere, they remained within the Malayo-Polynesian group until their transition to Cham-Malayo-Chamic, which likely occurred no earlier than the beginning of the Common Era, specifically around the 2nd century CE. Many scholars, including

linguist Blust, suggest that the modern Malayo-Chamic groups were present in Vietnam and Aceh from the 4th to 3rd centuries BCE. (Lương Ninh 2010, pg.243).

Due to the limited number of toponyms analyzed in this paper, an exhaustive discussion on the migration of Austronesian peoples to Southeast Asia is not feasible. However, based on the distribution patterns of these two toponyms and supported by archaeological evidence, it is hypothesized that there might be a group of Austronesian inhabitants migrated to Vietnam during the late Neolithic period via maritime routes from southeastern China. However, investigating the anthropology, history, and culture of ethnic groups living in the territory of Vietnam in particular, in Southeast Asia is an interesting topic but cannot be solved by archeology or linguistics alone. It is necessary to apply genetic technology. Therefore, this study, conducted as a case discussion, emphasizes the need for further research to achieve a comprehensive understanding of this topic.

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